

Guidance for Planning and Conducting Confirmatory Preclinical Studies and Systematic Reviews

AUTHORS:

Natascha Drude ,
Meggie Danziger

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Introduction

Concerns about reproducibility in biomedical research have led to a growing focus on the design, conduct, and reporting of preclinical studies. Over the past two decades, meta-research has identified challenges in the robustness and replicability of preclinical findings, often attributed to factors such as incomplete reporting, underpowered study design, and variability in methodological practices¹⁻⁸. These observations point to systemic pressures and legacy norms in the research environment that have historically prioritized novelty over confirmation.

Efforts to address these challenges have emphasized the importance of methodological transparency, rigorous experimental design, and structured replication. In this context, the German Federal Ministry for Education, Research and Technology Transfer (BMFTR), formally Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF), launched the funding initiative "**Preclinical confirmatory studies and systematic reviews**" in 2018, followed by a second call in 2021^{9,10}. The initiative supports:

- Multicenter confirmatory preclinical studies (Module 1), and
- Systematic reviews of preclinical evidence (Module 2),

with the overarching goal of strengthening the reliability, reproducibility, and translational value of early-stage biomedical research.

As part of this initiative, the accompanying project *DECIDE* (Decision-Enabling Confirmation of Innovative Discoveries and Exploratory Evidence; Module 3) was established to support grantees in upholding the highest methodological standards. The *DECIDE* project is embedded within the QUEST Center for Responsible Research at the Berlin Institute of Health (BIH) of Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin, leveraging the center's expertise in meta-research and research quality improvement.

DECIDE provides structured methodological support to funded consortia through:

- Interactive workshops on confirmatory study planning, multicenter coordination, bias reduction, and systematic review methodology;
- Individual consultations offering tailored feedback on protocol development, preregistration, and statistical analysis plans;
- Hands-on support in experimental design, including strategies for randomization, blinding, defining primary outcomes, calculating sample sizes, and managing the statistical implications of small sample sizes.

These activities are particularly relevant in the context of preclinical research, where biological variability and limited sample sizes can make effect estimation and inference difficult¹¹. Multicenter designs offer one approach to increasing generalizability and detecting potential sources of variation but also present logistical and methodological challenges. *DECIDE* assists research teams in addressing these issues constructively, with the aim of enhancing reproducibility without compromising scientific innovation or feasibility.

In addition to supporting individual projects, *DECIDE* also conducts meta-research across the funded cohort, including synthesis of replication outcomes and assessments of methodological quality¹²⁻¹⁶. These efforts contribute to a broader understanding of how confirmatory designs can be successfully implemented in preclinical science.

This document, *Guidance for Planning and Conducting Confirmatory Preclinical Studies and Systematic Reviews*, brings together the insights, practical experiences, and methodological

recommendations developed through *DECIDE*'s collaboration with the projects funded under the BMBF/BMFTR initiative. Originally created to inform applicants for the 2021 call, the guidance now serves as a general reference for:

- Applicants to future funding calls under similar frameworks,
- Researchers planning confirmatory or multicenter preclinical studies,
- Authors of systematic reviews of preclinical evidence, and
- Stakeholders seeking to strengthen methodological rigor in translational research.

The goal of this guidance is to support the design of preclinical studies that generate reproducible, decision-enabling evidence — a necessary step toward increasing the reliability and impact of translational biomedical research.

Guidance for Planning and Conducting Confirmatory Preclinical Studies and Systematic Reviews

This document provides guidance on multicenter confirmatory preclinical studies and systematic reviews. It is based on a review of the literature and interaction with the projects funded under the call “Confirmatory preclinical studies – quality in health research” by the German Federal Ministry for Education, Research and Technology Transfer (BMFTR), formally Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF).

The information herein was compiled by the *DECIDE* project conducted at the BIH QUEST Center for Responsible Research. *DECIDE* investigates confirmatory studies as well as systematic reviews and develops best practices together with the above mentioned BMFTR-funded groups and other stakeholders and experts. This document represents the current research status and should be seen as a guide that covers main issues but may require adoption to specific cases.

Minimum Requirements to Start a Confirmatory Study

Ideally, preliminary evidence should fulfill minimum criteria that warrant the step to a multicenter confirmatory study. Unless field-specific restrictions apply, those minimum criteria should (at least in part) be fulfilled before engaging in a confirmatory study.

- Blinding of previous experiments was at least performed for assessment of outcome, particularly if this outcome is subjective (not assessed by an algorithm or machine).
- Experimental units were randomized (independently and randomly allocated to experimental conditions).
- (Expected) Animal attrition and outlier removal of previous experiments should be clearly reported to inform inclusion/exclusion criteria for the confirmatory study.
- The primary outcome of previous experiments needs to be clearly specified.
- Basic quality management procedures in place like SOPs and published, complete protocols for complicated, non-standard experimental procedures; quality check for important medicinal products like antibodies, cell lines, etc. were conducted.
- In-house replication of main finding to substantiate the highly uncertain initial findings.
- Model is disease relevant, and limitations are acknowledged.
- Initial experiments/in-house replication were conducted on a sufficient number of experimental units to estimate effect size and uncertainty of primary outcome sufficiently to conduct a sample size calculation for the confirmatory study.

Experimental Design of Confirmatory Studies

The experimental design of the confirmatory study should reflect the initial design of the exploratory study. Crucial factors like primary outcome, essential methods, and model should stay constant between exploratory and confirmatory phase. Deviations need to be spelled out, motivated, and strengthen validity. To strengthen validity, limited extensions are possible. That is, confirmation is not necessarily a direct replication of the initial experiment. It is rather a test of the underlying knowledge claim and should enable decisions for future steps and translation into

clinical contexts. For deviations regarding the number of experimental units see statistical analysis and planning below.

General

- A flow chart¹⁷ including randomization and blinding scheme is helpful for reviewers.

Blinding

- Blinding procedures should be stated for all stages:
 - i. allocation of animals (to minimize selection bias),
 - ii. the experiment (experimenters should be blinded to the intervention),
 - iii. the outcome assessment (e.g., Imaging or behavioral testing), and
 - iv. the analyses
- If blinding is not possible on all levels a rationale should be given (e.g., experimenter cannot be blinded due to obvious differences in phenotypes of the different groups).

*Randomization*¹⁸

- Method of randomization needs to be stated including method/tool used for randomization sequence generation.
- If randomization options are limited for the experimental group a rationale needs to be provided e.g., due to social transfer of pain in rodents.
- Outcome relevant physiological parameters (like bodyweight or sex) should be included in the randomization scheme (blocking).
- If a subsample of animals is taken out of the experiment for specific analysis earlier, the selection of these animals should also follow a randomization scheme. (Consider immortality bias, i.e., if a substantial proportion of animals has reached a humane endpoint before a subsample analysis is performed).

Outcome Measures

- All outcome measures need to be clearly defined a priori (e.g., tumor growth or behavioral change) and preregistered.
- The primary outcome measure (on which sample size calculation was performed) needs to be stated and preregistered.
- Secondary outcome measures can serve as converging/supporting evidence Control groups.
- Depending on the experimental objective control groups should include positive and negative controls where possible.
- If available a comparator from standard clinical care should be included and a new treatment/intervention tested for non-inferiority.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

- Need to be defined a priori (= pre-registered).
- Should refer to animal welfare considerations (humane endpoints for the individual animal), animal model (e.g., phenotype or threshold for disease characteristic) and data (e.g., a priori defined threshold when data will be excluded or due to technical issues).
- Outliers should be defined across all groups and not only for a specific treatment group¹⁹.

(Animal) Model

- Limitations of the model should be stated:
 - What parts of e.g., a disease does the model reflect?
 - Are (clinical) biomarkers and/or diagnostics like imaging considered?

Quality Control

- Measures to assure the quality of medicinal product(s), cells, animal model, phenotypes should be in place.
- Strategy for the harmonization of protocols as well as trainings between different labs needs to be described.

Systematic Heterogenization

External validity is strengthened by introducing systematic heterogenization. Even though experiments need to be standardized between centers, systematic heterogenization potentially reveals important interactions of the genotype and the environment that also affect treatment outcomes²⁰. It is thus important that a) there is awareness of environmental differences between centers (e.g. standard food and cage sizes) and b) introduce a limited number of systematic heterogenization factors between centers.

This can be done on the environmental level (varying age, light regime, timing of experiments) or on the genetic level (different strains, homo vs heterozygous animals). Here a balance needs to be found between strengthening external validity through systematic heterogenization and comparability of centers. If a factor has been previously identified to influence the primary outcome, it should be included in the heterogenization scheme. Alternatively, complementing experiments within one center probe external validity by varying crucial factors mentioned earlier. Again, a balance between feasibility and knowledge gain needs to be struck here. Including both sexes in each center should be the norm (except for sex-specific diseases)²¹.

Statistical Analysis and Study Planning

Every project should consult a (bio-)statistician in the planning phase. Ideally, the statistician is available for potential consultations throughout the research phase. Analyses should adhere to the pre-specified plan and particularly demanding analyses should be closely monitored or conducted by the consulting statistician.

- Primary outcome should be defined a-priori before starting the confirmatory trial and should be the same (or similar) as in the exploratory study.
 - If devices are used from which several outcome measures can be extracted (e.g., gait analysis), pre-registering the specific outcome measure as a defined primary outcome is crucial.
- Experimental unit must clearly be stated (the unit that is randomly and independently allocated to experimental conditions)²².
- Sample size calculation (see below) must be based on experimental unit.
- To be able to evaluate outcome of exploratory study, give mean values and corresponding standard deviations ($M \pm SD$) of all groups (intervention and control(s)) as well as

experimental units per group (N) that these values are based on. Researchers should be careful to not mistake standard error of the mean (SEM) with standard deviations especially when communicating results from exploratory studies to study statisticians for the confirmatory trial.

- For deriving an effect size such as Cohen's *d*, a pooled standard deviation must be calculated across experimental groups.
- For outcomes which are presented as percentages to facilitate cross-study comparison and standardization consider providing raw values as well. Percentage value show floor and ceiling effects with regards to their variances when values approach 0% or 100%.

Sample Size Estimation for Confirmation

We recommend not to use exploratory effect size (ES) estimate for sample size estimation for subsequent experiments (within-lab replication or multicenter study). The exploratory ES is often based on a small sample and likely overestimates the true underlying effect^{23,24}.

- Instead, we recommend defining a smallest effect size of interest (SESOI) or using a shrinkage factor by which the exploratory ES is reduced. This results in larger sample sizes and a higher power to detect effects that are smaller than the exploratory ES.
- SESOI and shrinkage factor need to be substantiated.
 - When employing a SESOI, it should be stated whether the SESOI reflects a biologically relevant effect (to argue for a specific mechanism of action) or is of clinical relevance to e.g. predict efficacy of an intervention. This might vary depending on the research question. In the latter case, the choice of a SESOI should be informed by a clinician.
 - The use of a particular SESOI or shrinkage factor may be based on different considerations (e.g., previous evidence, practical constraints/feasibility). Those considerations should be transparently reported.
- Account for systematic heterogenization (see above). Sample size estimation needs to account for larger biological variability in the results in the confirmatory compared to the exploratory experiments. This can also be reflected in a shrinkage factor (see above).
- In more sophisticated study design such as using blocked or stratified randomization, for example, the blocking or stratification factor needs to be incorporated as a covariate in the statistical model.
- For the reasons stated above, using smaller or similar sample size in the confirmatory trial as compared to the exploratory trial is not recommended and should be justified explicitly²⁵.

Control Groups

- If two or more control groups are pooled for comparison against treatment group:
 - Establish that control groups are similar before pooling.
 - Pre-specify equivalence margin.
 - If similarity cannot be established: Which comparison (control – intervention) is most relevant to answer the research question?

Patient-derived in-vitro Models

- Obtain and store meta-data of donors. Such meta-data should contain basic patient data like age and gender and additionally disease relevant information. This can be incorporated into extended statistical model and analysis (may be a source of variance).
- Make sure structure of statistical models reflect repeated measures and biological units/observational units properly (e.g. through random effects structure in mixed models).
- Outlier criteria should be pre-defined.
- What are inclusion criteria for donors – how does this sample of donors relate to the superpopulation (e.g. all patients) of donors?

Subgroup Analysis, Sensitivity Analysis

- Consider clustering of data (e.g. mice of same litter) in subgroup analysis to detect deviations (e.g. prenatal disturbances).
- Sensitivity analysis could include different imputation methods e.g. multiple imputations, which can then be compared to the standard complete case analysis that might suffer from selection bias.
- Sensitivity analysis can also include incorporating baseline-values for outcome measures to assess robustness.
- Presenting sex-disaggregated data is recommended for meta-analytic purposes²⁶
 - However, simple comparisons between male and female animals are potentially misleading if no formal test of interaction was performed and particular care must be taken to describe results according to the hypotheses that were addressed in a statistical test²⁷.
 - If an interaction analysis is performed, results should be described as exploratory if the sample size calculations are based on main effects only. Be aware that power is usually extremely low to detect significant interaction effects²⁸.

Multicenter Studies

Specific Aspects for Multicenter Studies

- Based on the primary outcome of your study determine core results that need to be replicated across centers:
 - Core results are outcomes that reflect your main effect and ideally are gold standard measures for your paradigm (some examples: Stroke: lesion volume; Cancer: cancer volume across time and survival; Cardio: left ventricular ejection fraction measured via gold standard method).
- Balance cost and effort against the evidence generated when deciding which outcomes to replicate across several labs.
- The number of external labs should be limited (ideally not more than 2)²⁹
- External labs should be experienced in the models/methods you use.
- (External) labs can perform complementary analyses that need not be replicated across all labs but provide insights into patho-/disease mechanisms.

- Plan time and resources for protocols, work instructions and standard operating procedures generation/standardization between labs.
 - Protocols need to be closely aligned and differences between labs documented.
 - Protocols need high level of detail and reviewers in all centers.
- Compare controls/baseline of your primary outcomes to ensure similarity between centers.
- If animal experiments are planned make sure animal permit applications are aligned across centers or plan enough time for the application of all centers.
- Protocols and data storage and analysis should be administered centrally.
- Data formats need to be standardized across centers.
- Pre-define center-allocation scheme in randomization process. Prioritize covariates (e.g. bodyweight is more important than sex), which must be balanced across centers in case any imbalances arise.

Systematic Reviews

Valuable Hints

- It is recommended that researchers will attend/ have attended training in (preclinical) systematic review and/or have a systematic review methodologist listed on the review team.
- Search for already existing systematic reviews in the field of interest.
- Demonstrate need for the review.
- Complete SYRCLE protocol template.
- Describe strategies for data management and sharing and dissemination of results.
- Specify whether an information specialist (e.g., librarian) will be/has been consulted in the development of the search strategy.
- Specify at least 2 databases that will be searched, unless expressly justified.
- Specify that screening, data extraction and risk of bias for each study will be carried out by two reviewers, independently (or equivalent measure to ensure quality).
- Specify how the findings from the assessment of internal validity will be used to inform the conclusions of the review.
- Discuss how external/translational validity will be assessed, i.e., the features of the included studies that are specifically relevant to the assessment of the external/translational validity of the animal models in the disease of interest and how these relate to the translational potential of the findings (to humans).
- Specify how the findings from the assessment of external / translational validity will be used to inform the conclusions of the review.
- Describe how the outcomes selected for assessment are relevant to the outcomes of the human disease being modelled.
- If meta-analysis is planned, specify whether a statistician/methodologist will be/has been consulted.
- Specify what reporting guidelines will be used for any publications (PRISMA preclinical is under development, but the main PRISMA guidelines are relevant).
- Specify which systematic review data management system will be used, i.e. not Excel.

- Specify how, where and when data and code will be made freely available (expectation that these will be shared without restriction unless expressly justified). Should adhere to FAIR data principles.
- Financial plan should include project management costs.
- Work and financial plans should also include adequate time for training all staff who will be working on the review and piloting searches, screening, and data extraction forms to ensure quality standards.
- The protocol should be registered (PROSPERO for reviews related to human health) and/or published (e. g. on OSF or equivalent with DOI and timestamp) prior to the start of data extraction. This can be a work package and is not mandatory at the stage of proposal writing.

Two Example Protocols for Guidance:

<https://openscience.bmj.com/content/5/1/e100135>

<https://systematicreviewsjournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/2046-4053-3-48>

References

1. Ioannidis, J. P. A. Why Most Published Research Findings Are False. *PLOS Med.* **2**, e124 (2005).
2. Prinz, F., Schlange, T. & Asadullah, K. Believe it or not: how much can we rely on published data on potential drug targets? *Nat. Rev. Drug Discov.* **10**, 712 (2011).
3. Errington, T. M. *et al.* Investigating the replicability of preclinical cancer biology. *eLife* **10**, e71601 (2021).
4. Begley, C. G. & Ellis, L. M. Raise standards for preclinical cancer research. *Nature* **483**, 531–533 (2012).
5. Seyhan, A. A. Lost in translation: the valley of death across preclinical and clinical divide – identification of problems and overcoming obstacles. *Transl. Med. Commun.* **4**, 18 (2019).
6. Ineichen, B. V., Furrer, E., Grüniger, S. L., Zürrer, W. E. & Macleod, M. R. Analysis of animal-to-human translation shows that only 5% of animal-tested therapeutic interventions obtain regulatory approval for human applications. *PLOS Biol.* **22**, e3002667 (2024).
7. Simkus, A., Coolen-Maturi, T., Coolen, F. P. A. & Bendtsen, C. Statistical Perspectives on Reproducibility: Definitions and Challenges. *J. Stat. Theory Pract.* **19**, 40 (2025).
8. Lazic, S. E. Internal replication as a tool for evaluating reproducibility in preclinical experiments. Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2506.03468> (2025).
9. Internetredaktion, R. B. L. Richtlinie zur Förderung von konfirmatorischen präklinischen Studien – Qualität in der Gesundheitsforschung – - DLR Gesundheitsforschung. *Deutsche Zentrum für Luft und Raumfahrt e.V. - DLR Gesundheitsforschung* <https://www.gesundheitsforschung-bmbf.de/de/8344.php>.
10. Internetredaktion, R. B. L. Richtlinie zur Förderung von präklinischen konfirmatorischen Studien und systematischen Reviews - DLR Gesundheitsforschung. *Deutsche Zentrum für Luft und Raumfahrt e.V. - DLR Gesundheitsforschung* <https://www.gesundheitsforschung-bmbf.de/de/14868.php>.
11. Button, K. S. *et al.* Power failure: why small sample size undermines the reliability of neuroscience. *Nat. Rev. Neurosci.* **14**, 365–376 (2013).
12. Drude, N. I., Martinez Gamboa, L., Danziger, M., Dirnagl, U. & Toelch, U. Improving preclinical studies through replications. *eLife* **10**, e62101 (2021).
13. Drude, N. I. *et al.* Planning preclinical confirmatory multicenter trials to strengthen translation from basic to clinical research – a multi-stakeholder workshop report. *Transl. Med. Commun.* **7**, 24 (2022).

14. Carneiro, C. F. D., Drude, N., Hülsemann, M., Collazo, A. & Toelch, U. Mapping strategies towards improved external validity in preclinical translational research. *Expert Opin. Drug Discov.* **18**, 1273–1285 (2023).
15. Arroyo-Araujo, M. *et al.* Data analysis planning and reporting for confirmatory multi-lab preclinical trials. Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.31222/osf.io/cnuh7> (2024).
16. Rotter, S. *et al.* Towards better preclinical research: Key takeaways from confirmatory multi-laboratory trials and stakeholder discussions. Preprint at https://doi.org/10.31222/osf.io/hv5jp_v2 (2025).
17. Sert, N. P. du *et al.* The Experimental Design Assistant. *PLOS Biol.* **15**, e2003779 (2017).
18. Festing, M. F. W. The “completely randomised” and the “randomised block” are the only experimental designs suitable for widespread use in pre-clinical research. *Sci. Rep.* **10**, 17577 (2020).
19. André, Q. Outlier exclusion procedures must be blind to the researcher’s hypothesis. *J. Exp. Psychol. Gen.* **151**, 213–223 (2022).
20. Voelkl, B. *et al.* Reproducibility of animal research in light of biological variation. *Nat. Rev. Neurosci.* **21**, 384–393 (2020).
21. Clayton, J. A. Studying both sexes: a guiding principle for biomedicine. *FASEB J. Off. Publ. Fed. Am. Soc. Exp. Biol.* **30**, 519–524 (2016).
22. Lazic, S. E., Clarke-Williams, C. J. & Munafò, M. R. What exactly is ‘N’ in cell culture and animal experiments? *PLOS Biol.* **16**, e2005282 (2018).
23. Colquhoun, D. An investigation of the false discovery rate and the misinterpretation of p-values. *R. Soc. Open Sci.* **1**, 140216 (2014).
24. Colquhoun, D. The False Positive Risk: A Proposal Concerning What to Do About p-Values. *Am. Stat.* **73**, 192–201 (2019).
25. Piper, S. K. *et al.* Exact replication: Foundation of science or game of chance? *PLOS Biol.* **17**, e3000188 (2019).
26. Heidari, S., Babor, T. F., De Castro, P., Tort, S. & Curno, M. Sex and Gender Equity in Research: rationale for the SAGER guidelines and recommended use. *Res. Integr. Peer Rev.* **1**, 2 (2016).
27. Garcia-Sifuentes, Y. & Maney, D. L. Reporting and misreporting of sex differences in the biological sciences. *eLife* **10**, e70817 (2021).
28. VanderWeele, T. J. & Knol, M. J. A Tutorial on Interaction. *Epidemiol. Methods* **3**, (2014).
29. Voelkl, B., Vogt, L., Sena, E. S. & Würbel, H. Reproducibility of preclinical animal research improves with heterogeneity of study samples. *PLOS Biol.* **16**, e2003693 (2018).

Appendix: Glossary

Term	Definition	Reference
Accessibility of Results	The degree to which results are accessible, e.g. for other researchers, see also Open Access and Open Data.	
Between-Lab Replication	The process of performing a replication in a different laboratory setting from the original experiment. Even if the experimental design is unchanged, unknown sources of variation will be added to the replication and may contribute to generalizability of the findings (e.g., animal husbandry).	
Bias	Systematic error in an estimate (e.g., variance, effect size) caused by violations of assumptions, inadequacies in the design, conduct, or analysis of an experiment.	https://catalogofbias.org/
Blinding	Procedure to prevent performance bias. Will ensure that experimenters are unaware of the intervention condition during outcome assessment and analysis.	https://catalogofbias.org/biases/performance-bias/
Comparator	Comparator group acts as a control with an effective intervention (as opposed to a placebo group). Allows comparison of effect sizes between two effective treatments.	Active comparator arm: https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/aboutstudies/glossary
Confirmatory Study	A study aimed at corroborating empirically specific relationships between defined factors, based on previous (exploratory) observations. Results from confirmatory studies may verify a hypothesis.	
Construct Validity	Extent to which a measured outcome is representative of the phenomenon studied.	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1001489

Control (Negative/Positive Control)	A baseline comparison group that receives no or placebo treatment (negative) or an effective comparison treatment (positive; see comparator).	
Convergent Evidence	Convergent evidence refers to the ability of different measuring instruments to show similar effects in the same direction. (For example, measuring upregulation of mRNA should also result in a protein expression as measured by PCR and AQUA.)	
Data Management	Protocol describing data storage, data sharing, data preservation, and data Description.	https://www.dcc.ac.uk/dmps
Data Security	Models to ensure management of threats to data privacy, storage, longevity.	
Data Sharing	Making data accessible and reusable for others to different degrees by providing direct links to repositories or describing procedures through which data can be obtained.	
Data Synthesis Strategy	Strategy to combine data from various sources into one estimate of an effect (e.g., strategy for a meta-analysis).	
Design of a Study	The setup of a study, specifically what interventions take place, what measurements are taken, what procedures are implemented to reduce bias.	https://www.nc3rs.org.uk/experimentaldesign-assistant-eda
Discriminant Evidence	Discriminant evidence refers to measurements that rule out alternative explanations for the current evidence. That is asking the question of what kind of data would be necessary to disprove my hypothesized cause-effect relationship.	
Dissemination of Results	The way results are communicated and shared with peers and a broader public. See also Open Access.	https://research.uq.edu.au/researchsupport/ethics-integrity-andcompliance/researchintegrity/publication-and-disseminationresearch

		https://journals.plos.org/ploscompbiol/article?id=10.1371/journal.pcbi.1007704
Effect and Effect Size	<p>By the clinician (or biomedical scientist), a relevant effect may be postulated. From this an effect size is derived considering a variation when observing this effect. This effect size refers to a statistic which estimates the magnitude of an effect. In this context, the Smallest Effect Size of Interest (SESOI) is the smallest effect size that is considered theoretically and/or practically interesting and can be taken to justify the sample size for a given experiment. To determine the SESOI, previous evidence as well as practical aspects (e.g., feasibility) may be considered.</p> <p>The SESOI might be informed by a biologically relevant effect (size) that can be defined as an effect considered by expert judgment as important and meaningful for human, animal, plant or environmental health. It therefore implies a change that may alter how decisions for a specific problem are taken. In that line, a clinically relevant effect size denotes the minimal average improvement in outcome of interest to clinical decision-makers.</p>	https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-185X.2007.00027.x https://osf.io/preprints/psyarxiv/9d3yf_v1 https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.01.17.476585 https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/sim.4780050103
Efficacy of Intervention	Outcome measure of the effect of interest. See also Effect Size.	
Experimental Unit	The experimental unit (EU) is the entity that is randomly and independently assigned to experimental conditions. This is equal to the sample size (N).	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2005282
Exploratory Study	Studies that search for novel biological associations and phenomena without having previous assumptions or hypotheses, often employing less rigorous experimental designs, low sample sizes. An exploratory study may also be used to identify confounders (e.g., physiological parameters relevant to the research question). The result of an exploratory study may allow for the generation of a hypothesis that can later be tested in a confirmatory study.	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1001863
External Validity	External validity refers to the generalizability of a study and whether its findings are applicable or transferable to a broader context. External validity is potentially increased via replications between labs, tests in additional (animal) models, and consideration of both sexes. Whereas the introduction	

	of heterogeneity or multimodal studies can increase external validity, this can at the same time be a trade-off to internal validity. Vice versa, idiosyncrasies of a given experimental setting might reduce the generalizability of the study.	
Extraction of Data from Primary Studies	Process of extracting the relevant information to a synthesis from individual studies (e.g., an effect size to be included in a meta-analysis)	
FAIR Criteria	Acronym for data sharing standards: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable.	http://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-019-01720-7
False Positive	Statistically significant result obtained by chance when the effect being investigated does not exist.	https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.2738
False Negative	Statistically non-significant result obtained when the effect being investigated genuinely exists.	https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.2738
Feasibility	Likelihood that an experiment can be conducted under the given constraints (number of experimental units available, laboratory equipment, time, personnel).	
Independent Variable of Interest	Factor that a researcher manipulates within a controlled environment in order to test its impact on the outcome measured. Also known as: predictor variable, factor of interest.	https://learningstatisticswithr.com/book/studydesign.html
Internal Validity	Internal validity refers to how far measurements in an experiment reflect causal conclusions or mechanisms. That is, do we really measure what we want to measure? A proper experimental design will aim for high internal validity reducing potential risks of bias by introducing for example randomization and blinding.	
Knowledge Claim	“A formal knowledge claim [refers to] a statement that a research project/study has established new knowledge, or consolidated existing knowledge, with sufficient certainty that that knowledge can now be acted	https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.63294 https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000691

	upon. The required level of certainty might depend on the nature (risk and potential benefits) of the possible action.” Knowledge claiming research refers to studies for which any outcome would be considered diagnostic evidence about a claim from prior research.	
Long-term Safeguarding of Research Data	Preservation of data over long-time scales (at least 10 years). See also data security, data management.	https://www.dfg.de/download/pdf/foerderung/grundlagen_dfg_foerderung/forschungsdaten/forschungsdaten_checkliste_de.pdf https://www.dfg.de/download/pdf/foerderung/grundlagen_dfg_foerderung/forschungsdaten/guidelines_research_data.pdf
Metadata	Data about experimental datasets outlining content, timestamp, authors, explanation of variables.	https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18 https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618 https://www.jmir.org/2022/1/e25440/
Methods against Bias	Procedures to reduce bias in a study like randomization and blinding but also improved statistical methods.	
Multicenter Study	Procedure where multiple labs collect data for the same study design to investigate variability between labs to estimate generalizability of results.	https://journals.plos.org/plosbiology/article?id=10.1371/journal.pbio.2003693
Nuisance Variable	Sources of variability or conditions that could potentially bias results. Also known as: confounding factor, confounding variable.	https://learningstatisticswithr.com/book/studydesign.html
Null Hypothesis Significance Testing (NHST)	NHST is a method of statistical inference to assess the probability that the observed data (or more extreme) will occur given a null hypothesis of no effect of our variable of interest.	https://www.nature.com/articles/nmeth.2698

Observational (or Measurement) Unit	The observational unit (OU) is the entity on which observations (or measurements) are made. If observational units are not the experimental unit and thus mistaken as sample size (N), pseudo-replication is introduced.	https://doi.org/10.1017/9781139696647
Open Access	Freely available research articles for anyone, no subscription needed.	https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.8460.3
Open Data	Freely available and reusable data, without barriers see FAIR criteria.	https://book.fosteropenscience.eu/en/02OpenScienceBasics/02OpenResearchDataAndMaterials.html
Outcome Measure	Any variable recorded during a study to assess the effects of a treatment or experimental intervention. Also known as: dependent variable, response variable.	https://learningstatisticswithr.com/book/studydesign.html
Outlier	Outliers are data-points which are thought to present failures in measurement since they are too extreme to present a valid response to an intervention. Conventionally, univariate outliers are defined in relation to the central tendency and measure of dispersion of an outcome variable. The threshold values employed (e.g., 1.5 times the interquartile range) should be calculated from the distribution of a variable across all experimental groups and not separately for each experimental group to avoid type I error inflation.	https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/fqxs6
Statistical Power	Probability that a significance test detects an effect (i.e. a deviation from the null hypothesis), if an effect exists (i.e. true positive result).	https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797616647519
Preclinical Research Trajectory	A preclinical research trajectory comprises a cumulative series of experiments (including exploratory and confirmatory) that generate evidence to enable a decision to carry a newly developed intervention forward to clinical testing.	https://prod--journal.elifesciences.org/articles/62101/figures#content
Pre-Registration of the Study, Pre-	Formal registration of methods, experimental design, and analysis procedures prior to data-collection.	https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691618771357

Registration of the Study Protocol		
Preprint	Sharing of a manuscript prior to peer-review mostly on dedicated repositories like bioArxiv.	https://www.plos.org/why-preprint
Publication Bias	Studies remain often unpublished when an outcome is contrary to the initial hypothesis. This leads to an overrepresentation of positive findings impeding a meta-analytic assessment of the investigated effect.	https://catalogofbias.org/biases/publication-bias/
Quality Management	Procedures in a laboratory to increase study quality through standard operating procedures that ensure rigorous experimental design and reduction of measurement errors.	https://doi.org/10.15252/embr.201847143
Quality Assessment of Primary Studies	Retrospective procedure to evaluate whether studies follow reporting standards and whether they are at a risk of bias.	https://training.cochrane.org/handbook/current
Randomization	Assignment procedure to control for random variations between experimental units included in a study.	https://eda.nc3rs.org.uk/experimentaldesign-allocation
Registered Report	Type of article that undergoes a two-stage review. Before data collection reviewers assess the scientific premise and in-depth methodology including an analysis plan. Upon acceptance in stage 1, articles are in principle accepted independent of the results. After data collection, reviewers only assess whether experiments were conducted according to the plan from stage 1.	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41562-021-01193-7
Reliability	Reliability refers to the consistency in a measurement. In a broader scientific context, this means that a result is reliable if it is consistently replicated. A reliable measurement is not necessarily valid; for example, if results are reproducible, but do not reflect the studied disease pathology. The sample size directly influences the reliability of a result as uncertainty about the measured effect is (in most cases) decreased with increased sample size.	

Replicability (sensu results reproducibility)	<p>Replicability is the ability to obtain similar results by repeating an experiment with the goal of confirming previous empirical evidence. The replication experiment can use either the same or closely resembling methods (also referred to as direct replication), or it could include additional controls and/or conditions, a larger number of samples or animals than in the original study, with the aim of increasing and reaffirming the reliability of previously observed results. If the replication is performed in the same lab, it is referred to as within-lab replication; if at a different lab, it is referred to as between-lab replication. In the framework of preclinical research trajectories, replications are considered part of a confirmation process. Given that a series of experiments is needed to confirm a hypothesis about a directional relationship, replications incrementally solidify evidence supporting (or refuting) an initial claim.</p>	
Repository	<p>Online database where information like experimental data or analysis code is deposited and archived.</p>	
Reproducibility (sensu results reproducibility)	<p>Reproducibility refers to the understanding of experimental procedures and analyses in such detail that researchers can engage in a replication. Through this, researchers can distinguish between variability in results that arise from methodological differences and variability due to sampling variability.</p>	
Rigor	<p>The strict application of the scientific method to ensure robust and unbiased experimental design, methodology, analysis, interpretation and reporting of results. This includes full transparency in reporting experimental details so that others may reproduce and extend the findings.</p>	https://grants.nih.gov/reproducibility/faqs.htm#4828
Sample Size	<p>Number of experimental units per group, also referred to as N number. See also Statistical Power and Sample Size Determination.</p>	
Sample Size Determination	<p>Procedures to determine how many experimental units to include in a design. Depends on power, effect size, and significance level.</p>	https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.2738

Scientific Premise	Rigor of the prior research: strengths and weakness of the data and previously performed work upon which a study is built upon.	https://nexus.od.nih.gov/all/2016/01/28/scientific-premise-in-nih-grantapplications/
Search Strategy	Strategy to search databases for relevant studies, typically done systematically with a pre-specified set of searches and search terms.	
Study Quality	The assessment of a study's quality with respect to design, measurement, and question.	
Systematic Heterogenization	The process of introducing biological variation in the experimental design with the goal of increasing external validity and, consequently, amplifying the inference space. Although there is no consensus on which factors should be systematically heterogenized, suggestions of feasible and relevant variables include sex and age of the animals used and the timing of experiment. Systematic heterogenization can be introduced in exploratory and/or in confirmatory stages of the preclinical research trajectory but strategies for designing and analyzing these experiments should be determined based on its objectives.	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41583-020-0313-3
Translational Validity	Translational validity refers to the extent to which a scientific finding can be translated from preclinical to clinical contexts. For this, knowledge of limitations and characteristics of the studied (animal) model is crucial. Moreover, clinical biomarkers, pharmacodynamics/pharmacokinetics, drug dosing can be used as proxies to estimate how well the experimental evidence reflects the human condition and identify limits.	
Triangulation	Triangulation refers to the combination of theories, methods, or observers in a research study to increase the trustworthiness and validity of research findings. Herein, we refer to methodological triangulation in which different data collection methods (flanking experiments) are used to support findings from a (primary) outcome measure. Flanking experiments can confirm or refute a scientific hypothesis where one set of findings confirms, increasing the	https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-018-01023-3 https://ebn.bmj.com/content/22/3/67

	credibility of research findings, or refutes another set. Triangulation can also be a powerful tool to explain differing aspects of a mechanism of interest.	
Within-Lab Replication	The process of performing a replication using the same team and infrastructure from the original experiment. It implies that the experimental conditions will be very similar between both experiments, so it should be used to increase reliability of the results but not to increase external validity, unless changes in the experimental design are implemented.	